

Review Article

Evolution & Revolutionary Role of Softwares in Orthodontics

Dr. Harshita¹, Dr. Jitendra Bhagchandani², Dr. Vaibhav Vashishta³,
Dr. Tushant Rastogi⁴, Dr. Ayushi Singh⁵, Dr. Jyoti Yadav⁶

¹PG student
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

²Professor & Head
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

³Reader
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

⁴Senior Lecturer
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

⁵Senior Lecturer
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

⁶PG student
Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial
Orthopedics,
Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh- 226029

Access This Article Online

Website:

www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code:

Abstract

The advent of software in orthodontics has simplified the workflow, improving treatment quality and patient satisfaction. This has led to more people seeking dentition alignment. Orthodontists can now focus on treating a larger population, and software has made it easier to educate the public about the field, attracting more patients and attracting more clinics.

Keywords: Orthodontists, simplified, workflow, treatment quality, patient satisfaction, boon, essential need.

Introduction

The workflow in orthodontics which includes patient appointments, clinical and laboratory processes, patient handling, self-records, clinical management, etc. is a tedious task when done manually. The everyday advancements in orthodontics have thankfully made the entire process so smooth and easy, that the work efficiency of the clinicians has increased to multiples of hundred.

A typical sequence of procedures in orthodontic diagnosis, treatment planning and execution of treatment involves:

- Clinical case history
- Obtaining records
 - Photographs
 - Radiographs
 - Study models
- Case analysis
- Appliance design and fabrication
- Appliance delivery
- Evaluation of treatment

Initially, the entire record making process of model casts, photographs, radiographs and all was manual, time consuming and a hectic task, but thankfully in this digital era, multiple software are now available to analyse the case properly and the job of the clinician has reduced to obtaining one single nice scan.

Evolving technology and

integration of digital solutions in private practice have transformed 2-D approach into an advanced 3-D technique. Digital technology started to make its way into dental and orthodontic offices with the introduction of computerized scheduling in 1974.¹

Over the years, orthodontic practice has become paperless and digital photography and radiography have replaced their analogue counterparts and become mainstay. Record maintenance has been an integral part of orthodontics ever since its very existence. Today digital technology has touched on every aspect of orthodontic treatment and not only record collection and keeping.

“It has been said that in life two things are inevitable: death and taxes. May I add a third (though not so vital): the application of the computer to orthodontic research and diagnosis.” These were the opening statements of American Association of Orthodontists' annual meeting in New Orleans in May 1971.

How to cite this article: Harshita et al.:
Evolution & Revolutionary Role of
Softwares in Orthodontics HTAJ OCD. 2024

Traditional Workflow vs Digital Workflow
Digitization of Cephalometrics

Cephalometrics, introduced in 1931, is a crucial diagnostic tool for orthodontists. It was initially done manually until the early 1970s when Robert M. Ricketts created a computerized system for tracing cephalograms. Today, cephalometric tracing programs can perform hundreds of analyses simultaneously. In 1988, Dolphin introduced the DigiGraph, which uses sonic echolocation to gather cephalometric information, eliminating radiation. The DigiGraph consists of a digitizer probe, computer, monitor, head holder, microphone array, video cameras, and software. The digitizing probe sends sonic signals to the microphone array, which triangulates the probe's exact location in three dimensions. This allows practitioners to perform cephalometric tracings, analyses, superimpositions, and virtual treatment objectives. The DigiGraph's components include a cabinet with a digitizer probe, computer, monitor, head holder, microphone array, video cameras, and software.

Here's a brief history of how software has been integrated into orthodontics:

A number of softwares have been introduced and are into action since then, categories of their division being as follows:

I. Softwares for Office Routine Management in Dental Office

Dental office management software is crucial for efficient routine management and patient care in modern dentistry. It streamlines administrative tasks, enhances patient monitoring, and optimizes practice efficiency. Key software solutions include practice management software, which handles appointment scheduling, billing, insurance claims processing, and staff management. Electronic Health Records (EHR) systems revolutionize patient data management, enhancing communication and compliance with regulatory standards. Appointment scheduling software automates booking processes, reducing conflicts and optimizing chair time. Imaging and diagnostic software capture, store, and analyze dental images, enabling accurate treatment plans. Patient communication platforms foster patient satisfaction and loyalty. Billing and financial management software automate invoicing, payment processing, and insurance claims submission, improving cash flow and financial transparency. Integrating comprehensive software solutions into dental office routines enhances efficiency, patient care, and competitiveness in the healthcare landscape.^[2]

II. Softwares For Patient Education And Counselling For Orthodontic Treatment

Patient education software is a vital tool in healthcare, enabling individuals to actively participate in their well-being. It facilitates clear communication between healthcare providers and patients, offering accessible and interactive tools to enhance understanding and engagement. Key software solutions include interactive educational platforms, customizable health libraries, personalized care plans, virtual consultation tools, mobile applications for on-the-go learning, and health tracking and monitoring features. These tools provide engaging, easily digestible information, allowing patients to better comprehend their conditions, treatment options, and preventive measures. They also enable remote education on diagnoses, treatment options, and post-treatment care, fostering real-time communication. Mobile applications provide convenient access to health information, while health tracking and monitoring features enable patients to log symptoms, track vital signs, and monitor their progress. As healthcare continues to embrace digital innovation, patient education software remains a valuable tool for promoting shared decision-making and empowering patients to lead healthier lives.^[3]

III. Softwares for Cephalometric Analysis

Cephalometric analysis is crucial in orthodontics and maxillofacial surgery for assessing and planning treatment for craniofacial abnormalities. Software solutions for cephalometric analysis include digital imaging and tracing, landmark identification and measurement tools, analysis templates, treatment

simulation and prediction, integration with 3D imaging and Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT), and integration with electronic health record systems. These tools enable precise measurement and evaluation of craniofacial structures, allowing for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning. The software also offers treatment simulation and prediction features, enabling interdisciplinary collaboration and communication of treatment plans. It also integrates with electronic health record systems to streamline workflow and ensure seamless information exchange. As technology continues to evolve, cephalometric analysis software continues to enhance orthodontic and maxillofacial treatment outcomes.^[4]

VI. Softwares for Model Analysis

Model analysis is a crucial tool in dentistry for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning. It involves the use of digital impressions and 3D model generation, which convert scans of the patient's dentition into detailed, high-resolution 3D models. The software also aids in identifying and measuring dental landmarks, such as tooth cusps and contact points. It also allows for comprehensive evaluation of occlusal relationships and arch characteristics, providing valuable insights for treatment planning and orthodontic appliance design. It also offers virtual treatment planning and simulation features, allowing for visualization of potential tooth movements and treatment outcomes. It can also integrate with Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) imaging for a more comprehensive understanding of the patient's anatomy. Furthermore, model analysis software facilitates interdisciplinary communication, promoting efficient teamwork.^[5]

V. Softwares for Smile Analysis & Smile Design

Smile analysis and design are crucial in cosmetic dentistry, enhancing patients' facial aesthetics and overall satisfaction. Smile analysis and design software offers advanced capabilities for precise evaluation and personalized planning of aesthetic dental treatments. Key software solutions include digital imaging and facial analysis, which capture high-quality photographs and videos to provide detailed views of the patient's face and smile. It also includes tools for evaluating smile line and gingival display, tooth proportion and symmetry assessment, virtual wax-ups and smile simulations, color analysis and shade matching, and patient communication and consent. These tools contribute to the artistry and precision of cosmetic dental procedures, enhancing the patient experience and delivering aesthetically pleasing, natural-looking smiles. As the field continues to embrace digital advancements, smile analysis and design software remain at the forefront of elevating the patient experience and delivering aesthetically pleasing, natural-looking smiles.^[6]

VI. Softwares for Treatment Planning

Orthodontic treatment planning software is a crucial tool for orthodontists, offering advanced features to analyze diagnostic data, simulate treatment scenarios, and facilitate efficient communication with patients.

Key software solutions include digital impressions and 3D models, which enable orthodontists to analyze tooth positions, occlusion, and skeletal relationships with greater precision. Cephalometric analysis and landmark identification are also essential aspects of orthodontic diagnosis and treatment planning. Treatment simulation and virtual planning enable orthodontists to manipulate tooth positions and simulate treatment outcomes, enhancing precision and accuracy. Bracket placement and archwire selection are also digitally managed, optimizing biomechanics and reducing treatment time. Interdisciplinary collaboration tools facilitate seamless communication among dental professionals, while progress tracking and reporting enable orthodontists to monitor treatment effectiveness and provide patient communication. Treatment planning software also aids in patient communication and informed consent, making it a cornerstone in modern orthodontic practice.^[7]

VII. Softwares for Appointment Scheduling & Appointment Reminders

Appointment scheduling and reminder software have become essential tools in modern healthcare, streamlining the booking process, reducing no-show rates, and enhancing patient experience. These software solutions offer automated scheduling, real-time availability and resource management, customizable appointment types and durations, automated reminders, multi-channel communication, patient self-service portals, seamless integration with electronic health records (EHR) systems, and analytics and reporting tools. Automated scheduling reduces administrative burdens and offers convenience for patients. Real-time availability and resource management help optimize staff and equipment utilization, minimizing scheduling conflicts. Multi-channel communication allows healthcare providers to reach patients in the most effective and convenient way for them. Patient self-service portals empower patients to take an active role in managing their appointments, promoting engagement and accountability. Integration with EHR systems ensures alignment with patient health data, allowing healthcare providers to make informed decisions during the scheduling process.^[8]

VIII. Softwares for Bracket Positioning

Bracket positioning software is a crucial tool in orthodontics, allowing for precise and personalized treatment planning. It integrates digital impressions and 3D models of the patient's dentition, allowing for accurate analysis of tooth positions, occlusion, and surrounding anatomical structures. The software also facilitates virtual bracket placement, allowing for precise and customized bracket positioning for each patient. It offers customization options, allowing for a variety of bracket types and prescriptions, and preset options based on orthodontic norms. Interactive treatment simulations allow for real-time adjustments to optimize treatment plans. Some software solutions integrate with cephalometric analysis data to enhance precision. It also facilitates communication with appliance manufacturers, allowing for customized appliances. Additionally, it includes educational tools for patients, enhancing understanding and collaboration. As technology continues to evolve, bracket positioning software remains a leading tool in achieving optimal orthodontic outcomes.^[9]

IX. Softwares for CAD/CAM Appliance Designing

Computer-Aided Design and Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAD/CAM) technology has revolutionized the design and fabrication of dental appliances. CAD/CAM appliance design software offers advanced capabilities for precise and efficient customization of various dental devices. Key features include digital impressions and 3D modeling, virtual design, automated design algorithms, real-time adjustments, integration with intraoral scans and CBCT imaging, material selection and milling path optimization, collaboration with dental laboratories, and quality control and verification tools. Digital scans replace traditional physical impressions, providing a more accurate and comfortable experience for patients. CAD/CAM software also allows for real-time adjustments and iterative design processes, allowing dental professionals to make instant modifications to appliance designs. It also facilitates collaboration with dental laboratories, ensuring a seamless transition from the virtual design phase to the physical fabrication of dental appliances. As technology continues to advance, CAD/CAM appliance design software remains a cornerstone in modern dentistry, enhancing patient care and overall dental practice efficiency.^[10]

X. Softwares for Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is a crucial tool for businesses to reach and engage audiences in a competitive online environment. Software solutions for digital marketing include integrated marketing platforms, CRM integration, email marketing software, social media management tools, SEO software, content marketing platforms, analytics and reporting tools, and ad management and PPC platforms. These tools provide a centralized hub for businesses to coordinate and execute their digital marketing initiatives, align marketing efforts with customer relationship management, and optimize email campaigns. Social media management tools simplify scheduling, posting, and analyzing content across various platforms. SEO software

enhances online visibility by optimizing content for search engines, while content marketing platforms assist in planning, creating, and distributing content across various channels. Analytics and reporting tools provide data-driven decision-making, while ad management and PPC platforms enable businesses to create, manage, and optimize online advertising campaigns. Digital marketing software remains an integral component in the strategic toolkit for businesses to stay ahead in the competitive digital landscape.^[11]

Conclusion

The integration of software technologies in orthodontics and dentofacial orthopedics has revolutionized patient care and treatment outcomes. These advanced tools enable orthodontists to analyze complex structures, plan treatments, and visualize anatomical details with clarity. The integration of software streamlines workflow, optimizes practice management, and minimizes administrative burdens. Virtual treatment simulations are more convincing and appealing to the patients; alongside advanced data analytics drive continuous improvement, enhancing the standard of care and achieving optimal oral health and facial aesthetics.

Acknowledgements

- Author has no conflict of interest.
- Author has not received any funding.

References

1. Tarraf NE, Ali DM. Present and the future of digital orthodontics. *Semin Orthod*. 2018;24(1):376-385
2. Woollacott E. Best dental practice management software of 2024. TechRadar [Internet]. 2023 May 12 [cited 2024 May 22]. Available from: <https://www.techradar.com/best/best-dental-practice-management-software>.
3. Johnson AM, Brimhall AS, Johnson ET, Hodgson J, Didericksen K, Pye J, Harmon GC, Sewell KB. A systematic review of the effectiveness of patient education through patient portals. *JAMIA open*. 2023 Apr 1;6(1):ooac085.
4. Meriç P, Naoumova J. Web-based fully automated cephalometric analysis: comparisons between app-aided, computerized, and manual tracings. *Turkish journal of orthodontics*. 2020 Sep;33(3):142.
5. AKDENİZ BS, AYKAÇ V, TURGUT M, ÇETİN S. Digital dental models in orthodontics: A review. *Journal of experimental and clinical medicine*. 2022 Jan 1;39(1):250-5.
6. Us YÖ, Yüzbaşıoğlu E, Albayrak B, Özdemir G. Digital smile design: predictable results. *Journal of Experimental and Clinical Medicine*. 2021 May;38(3s):123-8.
7. Dipalma G, Inchingolo AD, Inchingolo AM, Piras F, Carpentiere V, Garofoli G, Azzollini D, Campanelli M, Paduanelli G, Palermo A, Inchingolo F. Artificial Intelligence and Its Clinical Applications in Orthodontics: A Systematic Review. *Diagnostics*. 2023 Dec 15;13(24):3677.
8. SelectHub. Best Dental Scheduling Software - 2024 Reviews & Pricing. Available from: <https://www.selecthub.com/c/dental-scheduling-software/>
9. Aldabbagh G, Omar M, Tayeb H, Alafeef R, Aldabbagh R. Simplyortho: a software for orthodontics that automates bracket placement. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*. 2019 Nov 15;28(15):98-112.
10. Jyosthna A, Xavier Dhayananth L, Evan A Clement, Piradhiba R, Navaneetha Nambi, A Review—CAD/CAM in Orthodontics, *J Res Med Dent Sci*, 2022, 10 (2):253-257.
11. Pooja R, Mahendra S, Arun AV, Reddy PV, Raju AS, Mahesh CM. Digital marketing and social media in today's orthodontic practice—Bridging the gap. *Journal of Contemporary Orthodontics*. 2022;6(1):1-5.